

Public Interest Documents Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

26/03/2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15320732](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15320732)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises responses from the workshop held on 25 February 2025 to co-design an upcoming ARDC infrastructure project that aims to deliver a platform that makes existing public interest documents (starting with Federal Hansard and public inquiries and reviews) easily accessible to a wider audience of researchers.

This project is part of the Community Data Lab, which fosters the development of tools, datasets and documentation that enable researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, museums, archives and other collections.

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. Since early 2024 we have been undergoing a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure. Co-designing infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders helps the ARDC to create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning new investment in digital research infrastructure for HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research data communities, as part of the [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

The HASS and Indigenous RDC began with the identification of opportunities to accelerate the impact of HASS and Indigenous research in the [2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#). The Australian Government Department of Education commissioned scoping studies to identify investment-ready programs, several of which formed the foundational activities of the HASS and Indigenous RDC.

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

The ARDC is currently delivering infrastructure in six focus areas, some of which builds upon foundational activities delivered during the first phase of the HASS and Indigenous RDC and some of which are new activities designed in collaboration with the research community. These are:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities
- The Language Data Commons of Australia
- Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
- Australian Internet Observatory
- Australian Creative Histories and Futures
- Connections

THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB

The Community Data Lab is an ongoing activity under the Connections focus area of the HASS and Indigenous RDC. Through the Community Data Lab the ARDC seeks to improve researchers' ability to utilise the data made available from galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) and other collections. This activity provides tools, datasets and guidance that meet needs shared by researchers with different research problems from multiple disciplines. The outputs of the first phase of the Community Data Lab are now available for use by researchers.

During the delivery of this phase, the ARDC developed a set of principles for the design of sustainable HASS infrastructure, which are (in brief):

- A preference for “infrastructure at rest” over infrastructure which requires costly active support
- The separation of data from analytics
- Efficiency and flexibility of platform design
- Reusable code
- Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents

The ARDC is now in the process of developing Phase 2 of the Community Data Lab to expand this suite of data, tools and guidance materials.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

We began Problem Identification in 2024, by calling openly for registrations of interest from partners who might be able to help us to design and deliver projects for the Community Data Lab. We targeted groups at universities that provide research software engineering and data analytics support to HASS researchers, because these groups have strong experience building solutions for researchers and exposure to a range of current researcher needs. We brought potential partners together for a series of roundtable discussions. Through these discussions we identified a set of possible projects which would each serve the needs of researchers from multiple disciplines across multiple research institutions, and which could be developed in line with the principles described above.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the open co-design workshop described below. The workshop was advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP

The proposed project aims to deliver a platform that makes existing public interest documents (starting with Federal Hansard and public inquiries and reviews) easily accessible to a wider audience of researchers. This project is being developed in partnership with the University of Queensland, Queensland University of Technology and Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation.

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

The co-design workshop was held virtually on 25 February 2025. The workshop was open to all and was attended by 29 participants from 18 organisations. Organisations represented included 12 Australian universities, as well as government organisations and research infrastructure providers.

The workshop aimed to refine our understanding of the challenge, validate the problem statement and its impact, confirm the user base for the proposed solution, and gather feedback on the proposed solution’s features. Dr Sam Hames (University of Queensland) presented on the challenge, which was summarised with the following problem statement:

“Public interest documents are records that shine light on the workings of government, including proceedings of Federal, State and Territory

parliaments, submissions to public inquiries, public hearings, Ministerial diaries, and conflict of interest and lobbying registers.

Significant efforts have been made to make these documents more openly available for interested parties over the past few decades. However, a ‘last-mile’ problem remains where most datasets of public interest documents are difficult to systematically consume and analyse.

This limits the ability of the HASS and Indigenous research community to draw insights from these valuable data sets. This is partly because of gaps in the datasets and partly due to the wide variety of formats and structures used. Significant data transformation and processing is required to make them usable which requires specific technical skills and expertise.

This leads to a lot of rework, repetition, and wasted effort on the part of researchers. Many valuable projects are abandoned before they even start due to the high cost for researchers to access these datasets.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1. A question register was maintained throughout the workshop to capture questions and comments outside of the scope of the workshop activities - this can be found in Appendix 3.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

Have we described the problem correctly?

- Terminology and clarity of the problem definition
 - Overall this is a clear description of the problem. ‘Public records’ may be better term because the focus is on things already published online
 - The problem would be better defined if it made clear the distinction between access and analysis
 - Not sure it’s about illuminating the workings of government as the problem statement says, but about looking at community expression in government outputs
 - ‘White papers’ and similar policy documents are not mentioned
 - The term public interest documents is very vague as these are quite specific government documents. Is this the best term to use?
- Project scope, sustainability and feasibility
 - Define low-hanging fruit to start with
 - Quantum of work required to transform documents/submissions

- Sustainability is an issue
- Do we have realistic, scalable strategy for content transformation across heterogenous formats and layouts?
- Metadata and findability
 - Findability of resources needs to be part of any effort
 - Even when information is available, existing interface can be quite clunky and not actually able to search properly
 - For parliamentary documents, sufficient and varied metadata is a massive limitation on both findability and searchability - this is not clear from the problem statement
- Analysis and engagement
 - Articulating the difference between access and use/engagement
 - On the analysis side, remember that not just researchers face this problem
Policymakers also need effective tools to analyse public interest documents at scale
 - Access comes first but is only useful if analysis can be done
- Existing solutions and comparisons
 - What solutions already exist in other jurisdictions internationally?
 - AustLII already has a Royal Commissions and Public inquiries Library

Who is this problem important to?

- Academic and non academic researchers including historians, linguists, policy researchers across a range of disciplines.
- Government and parliament
- NGOs
- Policy makers
- Public servants
- General public

Would addressing this problem be valuable (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)

- Greater accessibility and efficiency
 - Improved findability and searchability within and across individual documents
 - Putting more metadata into existing PDF public interest docs would be helpful
 - More efficient data collection, access to government information in ways that aren't time consuming. Efficiency and speed of lookups is the key
 - Making documents accessible without programming skills
- Policy decision-making
 - Being able to justify policy decision as a result of submissions
 - A better understanding of our past- what decisions were made, by who and how
 - Easy access to insights about decision-making processes and instances that have not served the public interest
- Transparency
 - Greater transparency of public decision making and how submissions are analysed

- Clearer tracing of public policy decision-making processes and the influence of particular stakeholders or problem framings
- Other comments
 - This is an important body of work in itself. Defining what the universe of public interest documents and where to find them would be of huge use to public advocates

Activity 2: Which Hansard records (Federal, State, Territory) are most valuable to your research and which time periods are you interested in?

- Federal
- State and territories
- Other jurisdictions including local government
- 18th-21st century
- Specific types of records
 - Standing Orders
 - Inquiry submissions, interim and final reports and Second reading speeches
 - Local govt minutes and planning committee meetings
 - Identifying speakers would be excellent and pulling up all the speeches from particular persons

Activity 3: Which public interest data other than Hansard records are most valuable to your research and which time periods are you interested in?

- Local and State government records
 - Local government planning submissions and Council minutes - especially very large metropolitan Capital Councils post 1990s
 - Documents for public distribution from all levels of government, along with versions provided in other languages. Collecting these together would make a multilingual parallel corpus, a resource of great value
 - Government archives
- Legal and judicial records
 - Court records/dispositions/findings and coroner reports
- Inquiries, commissions and committees
 - Proceedings and submissions to Constitutional Conventions - particularly 19th century state ones
 - Royal Commissions and other commissions of inquiry
 - Complete lists of public inquiries that have called for public submissions
- Parliamentary and political documentation
 - Parliamentary policy documents
 - Election related material - party leader speeches, voting outcomes, etc.

- Government white and green papers related to the conduct of elections, politics and Parliament
- Freedom of Information and transparency registers
 - Complete lists of FOI requests, linked documents if released, and reasons for non-release
 - Lobbying Registers
- Access issues
 - Not all public submissions are made public. This needs to be taken into account by researchers
 - Submissions that are public are generally not representative
 - How do we represent what is not public? Documenting what we do and do not get access to?

Activity 4: What methods do you (or would you like to) use to analyse public interest data?

- Search
 - Text searching within and across individual records
 - Vector-based semantic search across documents to find materials
 - Key word search
- Structured data formats
 - Plain text format (as opposed to PDF)
 - XML outputs are not ideal for general use. Humanities researchers need skills to analyse if this is the output.
 - Converting historic free-text/tailed data (like almanacs and yearbooks) into modern machine-readable data to flesh out existing datasets
- Computational tools
 - Wordcloud
 - Python, R, computational humanities tools, databases in SQLite
 - Voyant Tools
- Text analysis
 - API/bulk text analysis
 - Network analysis, thematic analysis
- Metadata
 - I would like to be able to search Hansard for metadata telling me when any language other than English was used
 - Comprehensive metadata
 - It is important to have metadata which is rich enough to allow splitting out parts of large datasets
- AI
 - There is potential to use LLMs for analysing these kinds of documents but we need to develop some guidelines before they're ready for public deployment

- RAG and LLM interfaces
- Accessibility
 - Good UX will be essential to allow regular people to access and use
 - Getting info easily is as important as later manipulation
- Tagging/coding
 - Grammatically tagged versions of Hansard
 - Consistent coding of topics and issues over time.
- Suggested websites to explore
 - <https://law.unimelb.edu.au/centres/ernn>
 - <https://www.aspg.org.au>
 - https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/wordcloud_cth.shtml

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close end of day Friday 23 May. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2025.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line 'Public Interest Documents'.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES

Full text of workshop responses

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Have we described the problem correctly?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The term public interest documents is very vague as these are quite specific government documents. Is this the best term to use? ● for parliamentary documents, sufficient and varied metadata is a massive limitation on both findability and searchability, not clear from the problem statement atm ● What solutions already exist in other jurisdictions internationally? +2 ● Where is demarcation between originating organisations and this projects ● Traceability of what organisations did across time and jurisdictions and institution - e.g. this organisation called xyz in 1932 submitted to Cwth enquiry, also submitted in 1933 when it was named abc to state govt ● 'White papers' and similar policy documents are not mentioned? ● Protocols for originating organisation may be an output ● Possibly - phased scoping. ● I'm not sure it's about illuminating the workings of government as the problem statement says, but about looking at community expression in government outputs [I will add: or the public records of government. and parliament!] ● (I'm not sure it's about illuminating the workings of government as the problem statement says, but about looking at community expression in government outputs [I will add: or the public records of government. and parliament!]) vector searching ● quantum of work required to transform documents / submissions ● Clarify cut off date for documents - how far back? ● Sustainability is an issue ● Retrospective - into 19C +1 ● Overall, I think this is a clear description of the problem. Perhaps 'public records' is a better term because by definition you're focusing on things already published online? [may I add: or you could use the term 'published' to make this clearer] ● Findability of sources needs to be part of any effort ● (Findability of sources needs to be part of any effort) Is this traceability to the original source or findability across a wide range of public interest documents? Being able to very easily search in one spot and know which sources exist... then to do a topic search to find across them - also easily ● AustLII already has a Royal Commissions and Public inquiries Library https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/ A LIEF project with a \$1.3M budget ,https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/, https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/ ● (AustLII already has a Royal Commissions and Public inquiries Library https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/ A LIEF project with a

	<p>\$1.3M budget ,https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/, https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/</p><p>
 Royal Commissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Articulating the difference between access and use/engagement ● Access comes first, but is only useful if analysis can be done ● Analysis use cases informs patterns of access ● Need to differentiate between access and analysis ● Do we have realistic, scalable strategy for content transformation across heterogenous formats and layouts? ● extracting data from PDF documents +1 ● A key addition for you (perhaps for the next stage) would be providing the context for public document sets. For example, the policy documents that led to public submissions and the documents the submissions influenced ● The problem would be better defined if it made clear the distinction between access and analysis - your work looks to be weighted towards access ● Define low hanging fruit to start with ● even when information is available, existing interface can be quite clunky and not actually able to search properly, find all that is needed +2 ● On the analysis side, remember that not just researchers face this problem. Policymakers also need effective tools to analyse public interest documents at scale +1 for sure!! ● It would be good to include policy documents in your list of public interest documents ● As a non-academic researcher and policy advocate, efficiency and speed of lookups is the key. This would make policy advocacy more accessible and democratic. +1 ● Yes (response from survey)
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
Who is the problem important to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● educators across a range of disciplines ● This will be used for civic work not just research ● Improved access to public interest documents is important to non-academic stakeholders like politicians and public servants. Broadening the user base would help with sustainability. +1 ● State governments - including them as part of discussion to reduce duplication and increase sustainability ● parliamentary scholars and parliamentary officers (working in parliaments) ● linguists of different kinds (eg. computational, historical, sociolinguistics, discourse/conversation analysis) ● Policymakers themselves, consultants they hire and NGOs seeking to influence policy ● legal scholars, researchers and practitioners ● Digital volunteer efforts in cultural organisations - including them in this - avoid duplication

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● policy advocates who are writing submissions and policy papers and wanting to contextualise current issues ● Speed of access ● (Speed of access) Is this the quantum of effort to access them, or how recent the public interest documents are? ● Example - Electoral registers - When have looked at current info, hard to then find retrospective (e.g. featured in almanacs, not data listsd) ● NGOs? +1 ● Policy research across a range of disciplines - not just HASS - science and tech policy issues also have inquiries and lots of submissions ● this process will be useful for other research documents, including those that need to be kept private. ● Will state parliaments be involved - change and standardise the origination document ● Very valuable for non-academic research e.g. NGOs, think tanks, anyone looking for good quality information about policy ● public sector POV? ● For people making submissions or giving testimony at inquiries based on submissions, it's useful to be able to find and read other relevant submissions from the same inquiry, but very hard to search/find them. +1 ● historians ● Hansard researchers ● non-tech people - general public ● Policy-makers, general public, community organisations, integrity agencies (response from survey)"
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QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Would addressing this problem be valuable? (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public policies are not always actually published - perhaps this project will be able to pull together those that are so there is a public repository of policy? (AustLii does so for law etc) ● greater transparency and accessibility ● If the solution provides contextual links to related items so we can see how decisions were made (?) ● Being able to justify policy decisions as a result of submissions ● If it makes documents accessible without programming skills +1 needs to be general purpose platform not too technical or intimidating ● a better understanding of our past - what decisions were made, by who, and how ● transparency of public decision making and how submissions are analysed ● being able to compare the submissions to a policy process with the results in the policy or its official discussion papers would be very valuable ● Yes. Clearer tracing of public policy decision-making processes and the influence of particular stakeholders or problem framings ● improved findability, hopefully also digital accessibility (WCAG), and searchability within and across individual documents. Which would

	<p>allow more efficient data collection and analysis methods and more accurate/complete research results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes, access to government info in ways that aren't time consuming if not impossible is essential for researchers and civil society orgs and industry ● Would be useful if it connects with existing databases such as APO and Austlii ● Creating a consistent interface for finding and accessing content would be a Holy Grail for anyone interested in public interest documents. +1 ● Searching through public submissions by key word etc to find those on one theme would be useful. +1 ● Murray Darling Basin Inquiry: now setting up requirements for new inquiry; could guide future inquiry requirements ● Putting more metadata into existing PDF public interest docs would be helpful +1 ● Better informed discussion of policy and governance has to be valuable! ● Easy access to insights about decision-making processes and instances that have and have not served the public interest. What is known and has been done about some topics at a national, state and community level (response from survey) ● As a non-academic researcher and policy advocate, efficiency and speed of lookups is the key. This would make policy advocacy more accessible and democratic. +2 ● This is an important body of work in itself. Defining what the universe of public interest documents and where to find them would be of huge use to public advocates. ● (This is an important body of work in itself. Defining what the universe of public interest documents and where to find them would be of huge use to public advocates) downloadable data
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Activity 2

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Which Hansard records (Federal, State, Territory) are most valuable to your research and which time periods are you interested in?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All levels from the 1950s onwards ● Are ephemeral records such as Hnsard editing guides (for both state and federal parliament) likely to be available? ● (Are ephemeral records such as Hnsard editing guides (for both state and federal parliament) likely to be available?) This material would be valuable for some linguistic questions. ● Federal Constitutional Convention Proceedings ● federal – all (ie. since Federation) ● all federal parliamentary committee records. Because I'm interested in the spoken evidence given to committees ● I am researching unparliamentary language which can happen anywhere anytime. Looking at variation by state and by time is relevant. So my interest is wide-ranging. ● (I am researching unparliamentary language which can happen anywhere anytime. Looking at variation by state and by time is

	<p>relevant. So my interest is wide-ranging) I made a dataset of interjections from 1901 to 1980 if that's useful https://github.com/wragge/hansard-interjections</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standing Orders as point-in-time regulations (ie not only current ones) would be very helpful for each parliament across Australia ● 19th and 20th century, state and federal ● (19th and 20th century, state and federal) from the beginning so going right back to the early 19th century. ● Federal, state and territory, all houses last 20 years ● All jurisdictions including territories ● As a housing and democracy advocate, Inquiry submissions, interim and final reports and Second reading speeches from 1949 onwards ● i would love to be able to do research on the Hansard and other Public Interest Documents from the 1970s onwards which is probably the messy middle bit with its own ● Access to transcriptions of audio/video recordings of proceedings. +1 YES! ● Important to identify what is NOT in any resource, so coverage indicated needed ● In general, material is more difficult to process the further back in time one goes. Recent material is relatively low-hanging fruit ● 18th, 19th century records with potential digitisation or OCR issues ● (18th, 19th century records with potential digitisation or OCR issues) State Hansards are all in different formats on different state parliament websites - interoperability would be wonderful ● NOT NEEDED - Hansard has a lot of bloated tabled documents that were of their time - extremely niche. Often Appendices - hard to identify - maybe could be coded in metadata? ● Set of really useful stop words may be useful (e.g. Gazette, annual report, notifiable instrument) ● (Set of really useful stop words may be useful (e.g. Gazette, annual report, notifiable instrument)) What is a "stop" word in this context? ● Local govt minutes and planning committee meetings ● Room for serendipitous results needed +1 ● (Room for serendipitous results needed +1) What is a "serendipitous result" , a fuzzy search that throws up unexpected documents? (instead of a structured search) ● From 2020s onwards/future Hansard ● NT Hansard is especially poorly organised / hard to search currently. +1 ● (NT Hansard is especially poorly organised / hard to search currently. +1) Make it big and capacious enough that there is room for serendipitous discoveries ● I think that relatively recent material will be of most interest to non-academic stakeholders ● Is it reasonable to start with newer and work backwards? (a: different formats pose different challenges) ● Identifying speakers would be excellent and pulling up all the speeches from particular persons ● Compare across states -= similar issues but at different times becoming visible
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All. since 1980s (response from survey)
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Activity 3

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Which public interest data other than Hansard records are most valuable to your research and which time periods are you interested in?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local government planning submissions and Council minutes - especially very large metropolitan Capital Councils post 1990s (Local government planning submissions and Council minutes - especially very large metropolitan Capital Councils post 1990s) Would be excellent, but also would be very hard to collect them all! Also noted that submissions not always public Court records/dispositions/findings and coroner reports - all time periods (Court records/dispositions/findings and coroner reports - all time periods) they are available, no? Proceedings and submissions to Constitutional Conventions - particularly 19th century state ones +1 (Proceedings and submissions to Constitutional Conventions - particularly 19th century state ones +1) Royal Commissions and other commissions of inquiry from the beginning to today Documents released under FOI Parliamentary papers [adding to this: there are many different categories of document that can be made a 'parliamentary paper', might improve searchability if these were built into the top category of 'parliamentary paper/] What is the official policy of each government? This is certainly in the public interest but not as rigid or as comprehensively published as laws. Senators MPs and councillors newsletters parliamentary policy documents documenting what we do and do not get access to (documenting what we do and do not get access to) Interaction with genealogical sites data aggregation Government archives, public submissions, published government policy documents, ministerial diaries Proceedings of inter parliamentary and inter council organisations Government archives - documents the making of policy and effects on community Research is subject-driven, so PI docs and Hansard will be valuable according to subject Government white and green papers related to the conduct of elections, politics and Parliament Correspondence to Committees that aren't published submissions (Correspondence to Committees that aren't published submissions) Court records - how to interact with something like FamilySearch which has much digitisation of random public documents Caveat: Not all public submissions are made public. This needs to be

	<p>taken into account by researchers. +1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● documenting why some things are accessible and others are not ● I once looked at submissions to a Senate Committee. Working from pdfs was not a great experience. And there is no easy way to figure out whether previous submissions to previous sessions might be relevant ● Party manifestos, constitutions and internal caucus rules ● 1/2 documents relating to the outputs of committees eg. committee interim and final reports and recommendations ● 2/2 other public documents and materials made available by individual parliamentary committees (eg audio and video submissions, additional information, media releases, daily programs) ● submissions are not all automatically made public (how do we represent what is not public?) ● Submissions that are public are generally not representative either ● Official biographies and CVs of politicians (versions from Parliamentary websites specifically) ● (Official biographies and CVs of politicians (versions from Parliamentary websites specifically)) Federal politicians have entries in the parliamentary biographies records, accessible through ParlInfo ● Complete lists of public inquiries that have called for public submissions ● Complete lists of FOI requests, linked documents if released, and reasons for non-release ● FOI Disclosure logs ● Lobbying Registers ● Registers of interests ● What is *intentionally* hard to find? Lists of redactions ● Documents for public distribution from all levels of government, along with versions provided in other languages. Collecting these together would make a multilingual parallel corpus, a resource of great value. ● Ministerial Diaries ● Australian Government Web Archive (part of Australian Web Archive) ● What is the relationship to Ancestry.com; Family.search - how do those docs relate to this project? ● born digital websites and how they have changed over time (wayback machine?) ● Policy documents produced by government departments/agencies in digital form and kept on websites (including the websites themselves) where MOG changes make the agency non-existent Example: National Water Commission ● submissions to inquiries as well as reports generated through these inquiries (response from survey) ● election related material - party leader speeches, voting outcomes, etc. ● minutes of evidence ● Easy to proliferate things that would be interesting and useful - how
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	<p>to assign priorities though is harder</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All time periods back to 1900, all Federal records (and state)
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Activity 4

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>What methods do you (or would you like to) use to analyse public interest data?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured formats would be helpful • text searching within and across individual records +1 • key word search • Analysis use cases informs patterns of access • plain text format (as opposed to PDF) +1 • Wordcloud of Royal Commissions https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/wordcloud_cth.shtml, https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/wordcloud_cth.shtml • Question: Has anyone looked at using Galaxy as an analytical workflow engine? https://usegalaxy.org.au/, https://usegalaxy.org.au/ • Structured formatting - can then work with/change as needed • API / bulk text analysis • Comprehensive metadata • Mapping (including of metadata attributes eg location, date and others) • Python, R, computational humanities tools, databases in SQLite, combined with human coding of documents • NVivo/similar analysis, tagging, coding, searching, comparing, mapping • I would like to be able to search Hansard for metadata telling me when any language other than English was used. • Talk to https://law.unimelb.edu.au/centres/errn Electoral Commission, https://law.unimelb.edu.au/centres/errn • Tracking organisations, institutions and Committees through decades of mergers, splits, name-changes and fallow periods - maybe also including local and state affiliates of larger national organisations as part of one umbrella +1 • Not just showing where things are - but methods to unlock needs to be shown to researchers • This is important for civic society • some way for applying Named Entity Recognition in digitised records (content and metadata) • Getting info easily is as important as later manipulation • Talk to ASPG aspg.org.au https://www.aspg.org.au - Parliamentary clerks, law librarians, https://www.aspg.org.au/, https://www.aspg.org.au • There is potential to use LLMs for analysing these kinds of documents but we need to develop some (at least basic)

	<p>epistemological / methodological guidelines before they're ready for public deployment (eg aiinfra.anu.edu.au). There are sub-methods to experiment with too: extracting entities and graphs for kinds of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I use a variety of tools from corpus linguistics / text analysis, including both quantitative methods (e.g. collocation analysis) and qualitative methods (e.g. concordancing to look at instances). The dialogue between the two approaches is crucial for me. ● It is important to have metadata which is rich enough to allow splitting out parts of large datasets. In the case of Hansard, this could cover obvious variables like party affiliation, but also procedural aspects like questions v. answers. ● This is an important body of work in itself. Defining what the universe of public interest documents and where to find them would be of huge use to public advocates. ● (This is an important body of work in itself. Defining what the universe of public interest documents and where to find them would be of huge use to public advocates) downloadable data ● The broader framework for the public interest documents should provide a more comprehensive and integrated view of government beyond just hansard plus inquiries ● converting historic free-text/tabled data (like almanacs and yearbooks) into modern machine-readable data to flesh out existing datasets ● legal analysis ● Text analysis (python/R), tokenize, SQL lite DB, ● XML - outputs . Humanities researchers need skills to analyse if this is the output. +1 this is not ideal for general use ● Voyant Tools - grouping info into a single 'big' document but too large for local PC ● (Voyant Tools - grouping info into a single 'big' document but too large for local PC) Word frequency analysis across the whole corpus ● Finding right way to describe any resource in a way that Humanities researchers will think it is for them - e.g. XML download ● consistent coding of topics and issues over time - using existing corpus? - If I see a topic tag electoral reform, how broad will I see? ● (consistent coding of topics and issues over time - using existing corpus? - if I see a topic tag electoral reform, how broad will I see?) Different research communities will be interested in different tags. ● Grammatically tagged versions of Hansard ● Human coded ● Good UX will be essential to allow regular people to access and use ● Scale is an issue - large sets of documents ● Linguists tools eg sentiment analysis etc etc are interesting but not the primary consideration for political scientists, historians, sociologists ● Public interface for regular people to use as well as something
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	<p>that people can download and analyse computationally</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consider how regular member of public could use this ● RAG and LLM interfaces ● Preserving commonly used, easily accessible identifiers ● Being able to build networks of those ● Differentiate between layers of data but also layers of metadata in the UI. ● network analysis, thematic analysis, analysis grounded in critical theory (e.g. Indigenous standpoint) (response from survey) ● enable both computational and non-computational research ● Vector-based semantic search across documents to find materials ● Semantic search ● see search term highlighted ● Capacity to search across entities within a time period - political reform proposals in x years no matter where coming from ● "consider stand-by citizenship. This is an open government project and can be a powerful tool to enable everyday people to engage with the democratic process. Think through their journey - they are time poor and lack expertise or a technical language. But when an issue or crisis animates them, how can they use this to quickly access contextual information, a single source of truth of government action, and be able to action that information to engage with politics. ● Need to have an intuitive, public facing UX" ● "(consider stand-by citizenship. This is an open government project and can be a powerful tool to enable everyday people to engage with the democratic process. Think through their journey - they are time poor and lack expertise or a technical language. But when an issue or crisis animates them, how can they use this to quickly access contextual information, a single source of truth of government action, and be able to action that information to engage with politics. ● Need to have an intuitive, public facing UX) xml training and support" ● Text analysis; quantitative analysis (eg regression analysis etc) - so being able to convert electronic records into spreadsheets; csv records etc - and to be able to convert images into jif/jpeg files etc. ● The easier it is to read, capture and then analyse data from the P.Papers, the more likely it is that these records will be used.
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Other comments

Security of the data is an issue. The 'safe vault' of electronic records of P.Papers needs to be AI proof - so it cannot be manipulated and history 'rewritten'. If the project proceeds as planned, the records held in this system are likely to become the 'go to' records for many researchers. It is vital therefore that there is a 'secure vault' of records that cannot be changed - and which is not generally accessible. Then researchers and others may access say - a 'working site' - so that if someone hacks the site/ attempts to manipulate it - any changes can be undone/corrected

APPENDIX 2: QUESTION REGISTER

(Anonymised)

Question	Response
Are there any questions about the approaches to meeting specific needs that have been outlined today?	
<p>Does “proceedings” include parliamentary papers? The real ‘meat’ in many parliamentary papers are in the annual reports, enquiries, Senate hearings etc - not just Hansard.</p>	<p>This would be great and has been discussed but there is a limit as to what can be done as a foundational project. Our vision is to make documents important to democracy in Australia accessible by all Australians. We want to work with a spirit of generosity of access. We are not about limiting, but beginning.</p> <p>This would be a big job for digitisation and very expensive</p> <p>Many Cwlth PPs are available in Trove: https://tdg.glam-workbench.net/other-digitised-resources/parliamentary-papers/overview.html</p>
<p>When tables and quantitative data will be recorded- will these be made easily searchable and transferable into other software (ie Excel; Eviews and other analysis software)? Just making pdfs is ‘good’ - but these are horrible to transfer into other systems.</p>	<p>I have worked with the Commonwealth Hansard software that Sam has designed and have been primarily working off a CSV. I would be happy to show anyone what I have managed to do with the search capability</p>
<p>AustLII has already published all Royal Commissions and Public Inquiries https://www.austlii.edu.au/au/special/royalc/</p> <p>Sure thing happy to discuss. We would be interested in some aspects of this project where it crosses into Public Legal</p>	<p>We would love to sit down with you and chat about the similarities and differences between what you have done and what we are proposing.</p> <p>We are all about working in partnership with what is already available. The intention is not to repeat what has already been done.</p>

<p>Information.</p> <p>Some aspects of Hansard are of interest to us - anything that leads to a legislative outcome. Our collection of second reading speeches and explanatory memoranda for example need expansion. We have tried to secure LIEF funding for this but no luck so far.</p>	
<p>You have mentioned historians and linguists as potential users - have you consulted with political scientists for potential use cases yet? How about non-academic users like political staffers?</p>	<p>We have showcased with some political scientists, policy researchers. We are keen to discuss further. Our initial use case was with a policy researcher in education. We are keen to connect with non-academics.</p>
<p>Security is an issue. Electronic data needs to be 'hack' proof and AI proof - e.g. a secure vault of 'perfect' records needs to be kept for future reference that is not used by researchers and others.</p>	<p>This project will not be storing versions of records for most data - those will always be stored by the relevant custodians of the respective data - for example the Parliamentary Library for Federal Hansard. Derived collections from this project will always be linkable back to that version of record in an appropriate way.</p>
<p>What is the rough timeframe for when we are expected to receive the compiled report?</p>	<p>As ARDC representatives mentioned at the end of the session, the report will be available after the co-design workshops are completed across the five different strands of the CDL. The last co-design session will be on Mar 25.</p>